

Polarization Modulation Techniques for Intensity Modulated Links

Meredith N. Hutchinson, Vincent J. Urick and Nicholas J. Frigo
US Naval Research Laboratory, Washington, DC USA

Abstract: The use of a polarization modulator for intensity modulation is detailed. Issues encountered are discussed such as the state of polarization drift over time for various fiber lengths and the nonlinear effects of polarization dependent loss on link fidelity.

INTRODUCTION

Polarization modulators (PolM) have recently been utilized for intensity modulation applications [1]. As covered previously, the alignment of the state of polarization (SOP) for maximum amplitude modulation is non-trivial [2]. It is well known that nonlinearities inherent to modulators can be used to mitigate second order distortion in the photodiode including via a PolM [3]. Figure 1 shows a link employing a PolM used for intensity modulation with the necessary components to perform the alignment for amplitude modulation. The purpose of this paper will be to introduce some of the issues that are encountered for PolM links that pertain to future applications for similar architectures.

POLARIZATION MODULATOR LINKS FOR INTENSITY MODULATION

Figure 1 depicts a PolM utilized for intensity modulation where the half-wave plate (HWP) acts as the bias tuning. The link has been shown to successfully maximize intensity modulation as well as provide photodiode induced second-order distortion cancellation [2]. Some of the inherent issues in the system include loss due to the HWP and polarization beam splitter, which is currently implemented via the Fiber U-Bench from Thor, as well as fiber stability. To study the viability of implementing a signal remoting link using a PolM, the SOP drift over time was measured for various lengths of fibers all of which are spooled. We define the rate of drift in SOP as a function of time over N samples as:

$$\frac{\Delta SOP}{\Delta t} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{S(t_i) - S(t_{i-1})}{t_i - t_{i-1}} \quad (1)$$

where $S(t_i)$ is the SOP at sample i in time. The rate should stabilize as the number of samples increases assuming the fiber is fixed and there are no significant environmental changes. The results in Fig. 2 show that over a large enough sampling time the rate of drift in SOP becomes constant for all fiber lengths except for 50 km, allowing us to analyze the expected rate of drift for different lengths. The instability of the 50 km spool is attributed to larger sensitivity to temperature changes as the samples were not taken consecutively. In order to implement a PolM remoting link, the feedback circuit used to maintain the proper SOP alignment will be dependent both on the speed of the alignment algorithm as well as the rate of drift in the SOP. Thus as the 50 km fiber in Fig. 2 indicates the bias feedback loop would need to be at the least 4 times as fast as would be needed for the 10 and 21 km fiber. A more rigorous study of the length vs. rate of drift would be needed to work out the feasibility for building a proper feedback circuit and need to include real world analysis of SOP drift, some of which has been covered in [4].

Additionally, polarization dependent loss (PDL), which is the measure of the peak-to-peak difference in transmission of an optical system with respect to all possible states of polarization, is of concern for PolM links [5]. Using a 1-tone input of 4.05 GHz with a commercial photodiode biased at 5 V and a photocurrent of 3 mA, the impairment of second order harmonic due to PDL can be seen in Fig. 3 in red as compared to a link with no PDL shown in blue. In Fig. 3 the PDL inserted corresponds to about 1 dB which translates to a SFDR penalty of 18 dB for these operating conditions [6]. The experiment is described elsewhere and is able to measure the PDL in the system which is well confirmed by the theory [5].

Finally, PDL for the various lengths of fiber were investigated over wavelength from 1528.77 nm to 1563.86 nm via the tunable laser source (TLS) in the General Photonics PSGA-101-A using the Jones matrix method. As can be seen in Fig. 4, the PDL can vary by as much as 0.5 dB over the wavelength range of the TLS where there is no correlation to fiber length. As has been studied previously, with a system containing multiple PDL elements the global attenuation is not a sum of each individual attenuation but rather a statistical quantity, rendering the analysis of such a system to be much more complicated than the treatment of one source of discrete PDL [7]. Future works plans to address the PDL analysis for multiple sources within a link such as presented in Fig. 1, including both passive and active components.

CONCLUSIONS

A PoM link utilized for intensity modulation was presented along with associated degradations due to PDL drift in SOP over time in long lengths of fibers. The drift in SOP was analyzed over a large number of samples to investigate the viability of a feedback circuit to correct drift which would be necessary for a practical implementation of such a link for antenna remoting applications. Additionally a discrete PDL source was analyzed for its negative effects on second order distortion generated in the link. Finally, a brief experiment was done to look at PDL in multiple lengths of fibers, confirming that analyzing and removing such effects for a long link will be a significant undertaking.

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Fig. 1. PoM link used for alignment of polarization modulator for amplitude modulation.

Fig. 3. Output RF power for fundamental (4.05GHz) and second harmonic vs. input RF power for a PoM link at the cancellation condition (Blue) with added ~1 dB PDL (Red) where bias is 5 V and photocurrent is 3.2 mA.

Fig. 2. Rate of change of SOP at 1550.52 nm for 10 km (black), 21 km (green), 39 km (blue) and 50 km (red) fiber spools for varying lengths of time at a rate of 1 sample per second.

Fig. 4. PDL as a function of wavelength for fiber spools with lengths 10 km (black), 21 km (green), 39 km (blue) and 50 km (red).